

ISic0940

I.Sicily inscription 0940

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

stone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Syracusae

Place of origin (modern)

Siracusa

Provenance

Catacombs

Coordinates**Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. □ ἐνθάδε κῆτε Θεόδωρος
2. ὁ χριστιανὸς ζήσας ἔτη β
3. μῆνας η ἐπ' ἰνδ(ικτιῶνος) ιδ
4. πρ(ὸ) ζ ἰδ(ῶν) Ἀπριλ(ίων)

Apparatus

Text of IG

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 492570

EDCS 39102097

PHI 140421

PHI 331431

Bibliography

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